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Multi-objective multidisciplinary optimization of wave energy converter array configurations and controls

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Abstract

Wave energy converters (WECs) can power Blue Economy applications (such as offshore aquaculture [1] and water desalination) and have potential for providing grid-scale power. In order to generate grid-scale power, arrays, or farms, of WECs are required. WEC arrays must become cost-competitive with other renewables as well as avoid leasing and spatial conflicts with other maritime markets. Therefore, this study uses multidisciplinary design optimization (MDO) to minimize the levelized cost of energy (LCOE) and minimize the maximum array dimension for an array of four cylindrical, heaving point-absorber WECs. To frame this MDO problem, the design variables are WEC radius, WEC position, and power take-off (PTO) damping with outputs of LCOE and maximum array dimension. The model consists of four main modules: geometry, hydro (statics and dynamics), controls, and economics. The formulated MDO problem is optimized using a multi-objective genetic algorithm (MOGA). The optimal design for minimizing LCOE is a WEC radius of 9.97 m, a draft of 0.997 m, and PTO damping coefficients between $3.7e5$ and $4.3e5$ N-s/m. This yields an LCOE of 0.117 \$/kWh and a maximum dimension of 80.9 m, corresponding to an array area of 2676 m². The algorithm places the WECs in a spread out diamond configuration where all WECs see constructive interference. For minimizing ocean space, the radius is 2.00 m, the draft is 0.200 m, and the damping coefficients range between 738 and 2028 N-s/m. This configuration yields an LCOE of 0.209 \$/kWh and a maximum dimension of 15.7 m, translating to an array area of 121 m². The layout resembles a much tighter diamond configuration where the WEC furthest from the incoming wave front experiences shadowing effects. The optimal design will depend on stakeholder budget and marine spatial planning requirements.

Keywords: wave energy; WEC arrays; controls; multidisciplinary optimization

1. Introduction

An isolated wave energy converter (WEC) does not produce enough power to justify grid integration, but an array of several WECs can. When co-locating multiple WECs in an array, the energy produced does not linearly scale with the number of WECs on-site [2]. The hydrodynamic interactions between these oscillating bodies can constructively or destructively affect the motion, and therefore power output, of each body in the array based on WEC geometry and configuration [2,3]. Additionally, utilizing motor-actuated reactive controllers optimized for maximum array energy extraction can increase array efficiency. Therefore, a search for optimal geometry, configuration, and controls of the array is necessary. The levelized cost of energy (LCOE) measures cost versus energy production over the lifetime of an energy system, providing a benchmark for cost comparison. Minimizing the array dimension decreases the ocean

space used, which is pertinent to marine spatial planning, or the management of ocean space for offshore activities, as well as keeping WECs within an optimal siting location. The geometry of the WEC, controls parameters, hydrodynamics coefficients, and the layout of the WEC arrays are interrelated and are treated as a multidisciplinary design problem.

These modules form the basis for a multidisciplinary design optimization (MDO), where multiple aspects of the system are analyzed and optimized for a specific objective(s) simultaneously. This optimizer seeks to minimize the LCOE and the ocean space the array occupies. The geometry module generates the WEC bodies and their locations, while the hydro modules compute the added mass, damping, and stiffness coefficients as well as exciting forces on the bodies. The control module calculates the optimal motor stiffness for each WEC power take-off (PTO) system based on the hydro outputs and computes the power output. Finally, economics calculates the LCOE based on annualized costs and energy production. This paper details the optimization problem formulation, model modules, and discusses relevant results and conclusions.

2. Methodology

2.1 Multidisciplinary Design Optimization Formulation

MDO problems require modules (f_{module}) to model each discipline, one or more objectives, and can include constraints. The formal MDO definition of this problem is

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & [LCOE, SPACE_{max}] \\ F(f_{geometry}, f_{hydro}, f_{control}, f_{economics}) &= 0 \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & 5r - \sqrt{(x_i - x_j)^2 + (y_i - y_j)^2} \leq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $LCOE$ and $SPACE_{max}$ (m) are the two objectives to be minimized, r (m) is the WEC radius, and (x_i, y_i) and (x_j, y_j) are the WEC coordinates. The inequality constraint ensures the WECs remain a distance of at least five times the radius apart to prevent collisions between WECs and provide space for maintenance. A visualization of the space objective and constraint is shown in Fig. 1, and Table 1 in the appendix details the parameters, design variables, constraints, and objectives.

This study optimizes for two objectives using a genetic algorithm, making it a multi-objective genetic algorithm (MOGA). Specifically, the heuristic algorithm NSGA-II [4] is utilized with the following hyperparameters: population size of 500, 100 offspring, mutation rate (η_{mut}) of 20, crossover probability of 90%, and crossover rate (η_{cross}) of 15. Hyperparameter details can be found in the pymoo documentation [4]. The input design vector is

$$X = [r, L, d_1, x_2, y_2, d_2, x_3, y_3, d_3, \dots, x_n, y_n, d_n] \quad (2)$$

where L (m) is the length of the WEC, d (N-s/m) is the damping of the PTO, and subscript n represents the total number of WECs. Fig. 2 in the appendix shows the WEC geometry variables. The parameters are

$$P = [\omega, A, \beta, N, CAPEX_{med}, OPEX_{med}, FCR, \eta_{avail}, \eta_{trans}] \quad (3)$$

where ω (rad/s) is the incoming wave frequency, A (m) is the wave amplitude, β ($^\circ$) is the wave direction, N is the total number of WECs, $CAPEX_{med}$ (\$/kW) is the median capital cost, $OPEX_{med}$ (\$/kW) is the median operational expenses, FCR is the fixed charge rate, η_{avail} is the estimated percentage of time wave energy is available, and η_{trans} is the efficiency of the transmission lines. The xDSM [5] diagram (Fig. 3) depicts the simulation models, disciplines used, and their interactions. All coupling variables are either explicitly or implicitly the function of the design vectors. Key variables used in the methodology that are not design variables, constraints, parameters, or objectives (meaning the user would never interact with them) are found in Table 2.

2.2. Geometry and Layout

Each WEC is modeled as a simple vertical cylinder (shown in Fig. 2 in the appendix). The initial array layout and WEC positions are randomized to reduce influence on the heuristic algorithm and find the most optimal conditions. Array configuration significantly impacts optimal WEC geometry and controls. This is shown through initial single objective optimizations finding the optimal geometry and control for WECs in three different structures (grid, line, and random, shown in the appendix Fig. 4). The resulting optimal WEC geometry and damping coefficients are shown in the appendix in Table 3.

2.3. Hydrodynamics and Hydrostatics

The hydrostatic and hydrodynamic calculations were conducted using a Boundary Element Method (BEM) solver and assume linear potential flow with linearized free surface boundary conditions. Frequency domain BEM codes can solve the diffraction and radiation problems of wave-body interaction and calculate respective velocity potentials (ϕ). This study uses the open-source BEM software Capytaine [6] to solve diffraction and radiation problems.

Heave excitation force (F_3) is found from the hydrodynamic pressure due to incident and scattered waves and the added mass and damping terms also calculated by the surface integral

$$F_3 = -\omega\rho \int \int_{S_b} n_i \phi_D ds \quad (4)$$

where ρ (kg/m³) is the fluid density, n_i is the normal vector, and ϕ_D (m²/s) is the diffraction potential. From the radiation potential, the added mass $A(\omega)$ (kg) and damping $B(\omega)$ (N-s/m) are approximated by

$$A_{ij} - \frac{i}{\omega} B_{ij} = -\rho \int \int_{S_b} n_i \phi_{ij} ds \quad (5)$$

These values are then used to find the WEC body motion and subsequent power extraction capability, detailed in the following subsection (equations 8 and 9).

2.4. Dynamics, Controls, and Power Take-Off

Using the results from the hydrostatics and hydrodynamics module – added mass in heave (A_{33}), hydrodynamic damping in heave (B_{33}), hydrostatic stiffness in heave (C_{33}), and heave wave exciting force (F_3) – the motion of the WECs and power produced for each WEC individually can be calculated. WEC heave motion ($\xi_{3,i}$) is assumed to match the following form

$$\xi_{3,i}(t) = \Re\{\mathcal{E}_{3,i}(\omega)e^{-i\omega t}\} \quad (6)$$

where t (s) represents time and $\mathcal{E}_{3,i}$ is the complex magnitude of the WEC heave motion (it also represents heave motion in the frequency domain). This form assumes the WEC motion follows the wave motion, i.e. because the waves are considered to be a linear time invariant system, the WEC is assumed to oscillate at the same frequency as the waves [7]. A motor-actuated reactive controller is modeled with two coefficients, damping (d) and stiffness (k). Reactive controllers using tuned stiffness and linear damping in the PTO are common in wave energy research [8]. Damping is a design variable that changes throughout optimization, and stiffness is calculated to ensure the WEC resonates at the wave frequency ω , shown by

$$k_i = \omega^2(m_i + A_{33,i}) - C_{33,i} \quad (7)$$

The stiffness magnitude is capped at 10 MN/m to avoid unreasonable controller designs. Using this stiffness, the complex magnitude of the WEC heave motion can be found using the following equation

$$\mathcal{E}_{3,i}(\omega) = \frac{F_{3,i}}{-\omega^2(m_i + A_{33,i}) - i\omega(B_{33,i} + d_i) + C_{33,i} + k_i} \quad (8)$$

where m_i is the WEC mass. Using this result, time-averaged power can be found by

$$P_i = \frac{1}{2} d_i |i \omega \mathcal{E}_{3,i}(\omega)|^2 \quad (9)$$

Finally, the individual WECs' power outputs are summed to obtain the total array power production.

2.5. Economics

The economics module serves to compute the *LCOE*, shown by

$$LCOE = \frac{(FCR * CAPEX) + OPEX}{AEP} \quad (10)$$

where *CAPEX* are the annualized capital expenses, *OPEX* are the annualized operating expenses, and *AEP* is the annual energy production. *CAPEX* includes the cost of each WEC based on mass, manufacturing, the cost of the mooring lines, the installation cost, and the shipping costs. *OPEX* includes maintenance costs, mid-life refit (a technological update to extend lifetime) costs, and decommissioning costs (all annualized). The median *CAPEX* and *OPEX* values reported by the OES [9] are scaled by WEC mass to approximate the final values [10], shown by

$$xPEX = xPEX_{med} + (xPEX_{med} * \frac{m}{m_{max}}) \quad (11)$$

where *xPEX* represents either *CAPEX* or *OPEX*, and *m_{max}* (kg) is the mass of the most massive WEC included in the EOS report. Scaling in this manner ensures the modeled cost of the WECs falls within the median and maximum *xPEX* values. The reported *xPEX* values are normalized by the rated power, so they must be multiplied by the rated power of the modeled WECs. The annual energy production is calculated by

$$AEP = P * \eta_{trans} * \eta_{avail} \quad (12)$$

where η_{trans} and η_{avail} account for losses due to transmission lines and availability of wave power, respectively. Conservative values of $\eta_{trans} = 0.945$ and $\eta_{avail} = 0.95$ are used in this study.

2.6. Validation

The model was validated against the LCOEs for a variety of wave energy devices calculated by NREL [11]. The design used for validation was a single, cylindrical WEC with a radius of 10 m, a length of 5.2 m, and a damping of 100,000 N-s/m, these sizes are on scale with the WECs used in the NREL study. The tuned PTO stiffness was also set to zero because the NREL LCOE calculations did not account for tuned controls. The LCOE from the model with this design input was 2.27 \$/kWh, which sits in the range of the LCOEs reported by NREL (0.67 \$/kWh - 4.79 \$/kWh). The difference between the LCOEs could be accounted for by differences in geometry, wave spectra, and control parameters, but still falls in a reasonable range.

3. Results

The Pareto front, shown in Fig. 5, depicts the trade-off between minimizing ocean space and minimizing LCOE, found from solving Eq. 1. The minimized LCOE configuration and minimized array dimension and their resulting wave perturbation fields can be seen in Figs. 6 and 7, respectively. The optimized WEC geometry and controller can be found in Table 4 in the appendix. The lowest LCOE requires a relatively large amount of ocean space and WEC radii that are nearly five times that of the minimized ocean space solution. The lowest ocean space solution shows an 80.6% reduction in ocean space used compared to the minimized LCOE; however, there is a 44.0% increase in LCOE. In the minimal LCOE case, all PTO damping coefficients stay between $3.7e^5$ and $4.3e^5$ N-s/m. However, these coefficients vary more broadly (between 738 and 2028 N-s/m) in the minimal array dimension case. This is likely the result of the PTO system needing to compensate for the lack of ideal WEC placement. For minimizing LCOE, the optimizer places the WECs such that bodies 2, 3, and 4 experience a wave elevation greater than what they would have if they were isolated. At the other end of the Pareto front, the optimizer attempts to do the same, but

sacrifices the maximum power production of body 3 to maintain array compactness. The optimization took 36.6 hours to run on a machine with 28x Intel Core i9-10940X CPU @3.30 GHz and 251.4 GiB of memory.

4. **Conclusion**

For both objectives, the algorithm found the optimal configuration to resemble a diamond formation. This indicates that the wake of upstream WECs can be constructive to the power production of WECs downstream if placed correctly. The diamond configuration, at varying levels of compactness, is optimal for four WEC arrays in terms of minimizing both LCOE and ocean space. However, more compact configurations will require more precise controls in order to reduce energy losses. The LCOEs reported are relatively low compared to the NREL reference models, which report LCOEs of a single WEC between 0.31 and 1.47 \$/kWh as of 2015 [11]. This is likely due to the inconsistencies in modeling and reporting LCOE in marine renewable energy. This study utilizes a mass-scaling method of CAPEX and OPEX values from existing WECs rather than estimating their theoretical costs. If actualized, the array LCOE would likely be higher than the values reported here. However, the simulation results still indicate optimal configurations for maximizing power production and minimizing mass. Future work should include a more detailed cost model to better compare array performance or be optimized by a different metric than LCOE.

Existing WEC farms are not available to compare maximum dimensions and power output. However, the configurations found in this study use significantly less ocean space than existing and developing offshore wind farms. The Block Island Wind Farm hosts five, 6 MW turbines across approximately 0.9 km² (maximum dimension 6 km), producing around 2.04e⁷ kWh/km² annually with an LCOE of 0.244 \$/kWh [12]. The largest WEC array dimension reported in this study is 0.0809 km, or 0.0027 km², producing around 1.86e¹⁰ kWh/km² annually. The smallest array dimension of 0.0157 km (0.000121 km²) produces 2.03e¹¹ kWh/km² annually. It is likely this model overpredicts power produced, also contributing to the low LCOE values. However, wave energy is more dense than offshore wind, so it is also possible that wave energy is a more efficient use of ocean space than offshore wind.

The computational cost of this study was significant for four bodies. Increasing the number of bodies in the array increased the computational cost non-linearly, indicating this method is not sustainable for large arrays. Future work could include implementing a fast-approaching approximation model [13] and efficient computational tools such as GPUs. Mooring and transmission lines are not considered in the dynamics; however, future work should model their effect on body motion and power output. Additionally, investigating the cost savings of shared mooring lines could impact optimal LCOE configurations, making tighter configurations more favorable. To further improve fidelity of the model, irregular sea-state spectra should be used rather than one dominant frequency. Additionally, time-domain analysis could be implemented to better optimize the control system.

The final objective of this study is to provide high-fidelity guidance to WEC array designers and stakeholders by providing Pareto-optimal designs for their analysis and requirements.

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Appendix A. Figures and tables.

Fig 1. Plot showing what the constraint variable $SPACE_{MIN}$ and the objective variable $SPACE_{MAX}$ represent.

Table 1. Table outlining parameters, design variables, constraints, and objectives.

Variable Name	Symbol	Units	Type	Notes/Bounds/Value Used
Wave Frequency	ω	rad/s	Parameter	1.047 rad/s
Wave Amplitude	A	m	Parameter	1 m
Wave Direction	β	$^{\circ}$	Parameter	0 rad measured from positive x-axis
Number of WECs	N	-	Parameter	4 WECs
Median Capital Expenses	$CAPEX_{MED}$	\$/kW	Parameter	\$9000/kW
Median Operating Expenses	$OPEX_{MED}$	\$/kW	Parameter	\$450/kW
Fixed Charge Rate	FCR	-	Parameter	10.8%
Wave Energy Availability	η_{avail}	-	Parameter	95%
Transmission Line Efficiency	η_{trans}	-	Parameter	94.5%

WEC Radius	r	m	Design Variable	ranges from 2 to 10 m
WEC Length	L	m	Design Variable	ranges from $0.1r$ to $0.5r$
X Location	x_i	m	Design Variable	ranges from -2500 to 2500 m, x_i is 0
Y Location	y_i	m	Design Variable	ranges from -2500 to 2500 m, y_i is 0
PTO Damping	d_i	N-s/m	Design Variable	ranges from 1 to 10,000,000 Ns/m
Minimum WEC Spacing	$SPACE_{MIN}$	m	Constraint	must be larger than $10r$, see Fig 1. for a visualization
Levelized Cost of Energy	$LCOE$	\$/kWh	Objective	-
Maximum WEC Spacing	$SPACE_{MAX}$	m	Objective	See Fig 1. for a visualization

Fig 2. Cylindrical WEC, with design variables (radius (r), length (L), and PTO damping (d)) identified. PTO stiffness (k) is also identified, but is calculated in the model and not a design variable. The PTO damping and stiffness combine to mathematically and schematically represent the motor-actuated controller.

Fig 3. xDSM diagram of coupled MDO MOGA problem.

Table 2. Important variables wrapped in the model. These are variables that appear in the methodology, but a user of the code would not interact with.

Name	Symbol	Units	Module(s)
Heave Exciting Force	$F_{3,i}$	N	Hydro - calculated, Controls - used
Diffraction Potential	φ_D	m^2/s	Hydro
Added Mass Heave	$A_{33,i}$	kg	Hydro - calculated, Controls - used
Wave Damping Heave	$B_{33,i}$	N-s/m	Hydro - calculated, Controls - used
Hydrostatic Stiffness	$C_{33,i}$	N/m	Hydro - calculated, Controls - used
WEC mass	m_i	kg	Hydro - calculated, Controls - used
WEC PTO stiffness	k_i	N/m	Controls
WEC Heave Motion	$\xi_{3,i}$	m	Controls
WEC Heave Motion Complex Magnitude	$\tilde{\xi}_{3,i}$	m	Controls
Mechanical Power	P_i	kW	Controls - calculated, Economics - used
Expected Expenses	$xPEX$	\$	Economics
Annual Energy Production	AEP	kWh	Economics

Fig 4. Grid, line, and random layout used in single objective geometry and controls optimization. Optimal WEC geometry and dampings are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Optimal geometry and dampings for fixed layouts shown in Fig. 4.

Layout	r	L	d_1	d_2	d_3	d_4
Grid	2.37	0.237	3137	2991	3528	2950
Line	8.98	0.898	261323	306800	324673	250521
Random	4.24	0.424	22629	23760	21057	25399

Fig 5. Pareto front of the MOGA optimization showing the trade-off between minimizing ocean space and minimizing LCOE.

Fig 6. Array configuration and wave field perturbation for minimized LCOE.

Fig 7. Array configuration and wave field perturbation for minimized ocean space.

Table 4. WEC geometry and controls for optimized WEC arrays.

Minimized Objective	r (m)	L (m)	d_1 (N-s/m)	d_2 (N-s/m)	d_3 (N-s/m)	d_4 (N-s/m)
LCOE	9.97	0.997	376275	434758	404316	397325
Ocean Space	2.00	0.200	738	1715	2028	374